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**NECESSITY, CONCEPT AND PRINCIPLES FOR INTRODUCING
ACCOUNTING POLICY IN THE ACTIVITIES
OF ECONOMIC ENTITIES**

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the consideration of the issues of organizing and keeping the accounting policy, its principles and conceptual foundations in the activities of economic entities. In addition, the article reveals accounting policy requirements in compliance with the international financial reporting standards, as well as proposes the method for transforming the national accounting system to the IFRS.

Keywords: Accounting policy, international standards, conceptual framework, principles of accounting policy, chart of accounts.

The aim of the accounting policy in the field of accounting of an economic entity is to ensure the homogeneity, unity and identity of methods, tools and techniques for accounting purposes and taxation purposes.

Any accounting policy is typically based on International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Accounting”, the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, National Accounting Standards №1 “Accounting Policies and Financial Reporting” (NAS №1), etc.

The methods of handling book-keeping and tax accounting and reflecting business transactions in accounting can be chosen by the accounting and reporting service unit of the enterprise itself. Further, it is approved by the head of the

economic entity. It is confirmed of the enterprise. Only then it will be considered effective and have legal force.

In the process of organizing the Accounting Policy, the technological and institutional peculiarities of the activity of the economic entity, the organizational structure, the properties of the formation of financial results, and international experience in this industry should be taken into consideration.

If the financial statements are prepared in compliance with the requirements of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), then the consolidation process is adjusted to the instructions of the Parent Company

An approximate structure of the Accounting policy of the economic entity looks like this:

- introduction;
- general provisions;
- organization of accounting;
- internal control and audit system;
- document flow and business operations;
- long-term assets;
- intangible assets;
- current assets;
- assets and liabilities denominated in foreign currency;
- inventory;
- cost accounting and prime-cost calculation of products;
- accounting for the formation of financial results and the identification of income;
- the procedure for accounting for wages;
- income taxation;
- financial statements.

Financial accounting is organized in compliance with the Law on Accounting of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Accounting Standards (NAS) and other

legislative acts and instructions registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the account of the requirements of international accounting standards.

Herewith the role of the working chart of accounts, which is a set of analytical and synthetic accounts of accounting, aligned with the articles of financial statements, is of great importance.

An economic entity during the reporting period (from January 1 to December 31) has the right to make amendments to the Chart of Accounts for Production and Economic Activities.

As the practice for applying accounting policies demonstrates, when implementing the IFRS in Uzbekistan, the transition immediately to the IFRS seems difficult due to the developed accounting system, which needs to be transformed step by step and sequentially. This necessitates the use of 2 Charts of Accounts: Chart of Accounts according to the NAS and Chart of Accounts according to the IFRS.

According to paragraph 8 of International Financial Reporting Standard (IAS) 8 “Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors”, an accounting policy is established that, in the opinion of the IASB, results in the formation of financial statements containing relevant and reliable information about transactions, other events and the conditions to which the accounting policy applies. The application of the specified accounting policy is not compulsory in cases where the effect of its application is insignificant [2].

The accounting policy should adhere to the basic principles of accounting such as: continuity, reliability, comparability of indicators [1]. In addition to these principles, which are indicated in Article 3 of the Law “On Accounting to the Republic of Uzbekistan”, there are other essential principles in international accounting practice, including the following:

- accrual principle;
- double entry accounting;

monetary value of business transactions, assets and liabilities;
foresight (caution);
predominance of content over form;
neutrality of financial statements;
actual valuation of assets and liabilities;
compliance of income and expenses of the reporting period;
understandability;
significance;
materiality;
true and impartial presentation;
completeness;
subsequence;
timeliness;
offsetting (netting of articles) [5].

Investigation of the international experience of US companies shows the diversity and detail of sections and articles of accounting policy according to the national standard US GAAP. Moreover, in the US accounting policy particular focus is made on cash and its equivalent, the prime-cost of goods, finished products and services, receivables and payables, credit risks, government assistance and grants, equity securities without an easily determinable fair value, etc. [4].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the need and relevance of introducing the accounting policy is increasing in the context of the transformation of the economy of Uzbekistan to international accounting and financial reporting standards. This is especially necessary during the period of ensuring economic growth in the volume of production of economic entities.

Reference:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Accounting” dated April 13, 2016.

2. International Financial Reporting Standard (IAS) 8 “Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors”. <https://nrm.uz>
3. IAS 8 - Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors. 2005. 01.01. www.iasplus.com/en/standards/ias/ias8
4. US GAAP Disclosure List. Accounting Policies. <https://www.readyratios.com/usgaap/AccountingPolicies/>
5. Accounting Policy Representative office of FINEX in the Republic of Uzbekistan for accounting and taxation purposes. <https://finex.uz>.